

Blue Nature-Based Solutions in marine and coastal EU policies: Challenges, recommendations and policy opportunities throughout the policy cycle

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ABSTRACT

The paper focuses on the use of Nature-based solutions (NBS) in European marine and coastal governance – also called marine or blue NBS. Such solutions appear to be promising tools to deal with interdependent challenges such as climate change adaptation, biodiversity conservation and restoration, and sustainable development. Numerous research projects have demonstrated their utility and investigated the best ways to implement them. In addition, NBS are supported by international networks and agreements, and advocated by actors active at the international and European Union (EU) levels. However, blue NBS are mostly absent from EU policies (directives and regulations) and national, regional and local implementation of those policies. In this paper, barriers to the uptake of NBS at each step of the policy cycle are investigated: agenda-setting, policy formulation, decision-making, policy implementation, and policy evaluation. Policy recommendations and related EU policy opportunities for each of these steps are then presented.

1. Introduction

Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) offer promising avenues for addressing various environmental, social, and economic challenges facing Europe in the 21st century [70]. They are defined by the European Commission (EC) as ‘solutions that are inspired and supported by nature, which are cost-effective, simultaneously provide environmental, social and economic benefits and help build resilience [...] Nature-based solutions must therefore benefit biodiversity and support the delivery of a range of ecosystem services’ ([92], p.3). NBS are indeed valuable instruments for tackling both climate change and enhancing biodiversity restoration, while supporting sustainable development [83].

NBS encompass a range of strategies that utilise natural processes and ecosystems to address societal challenges [79]. These solutions include protection, restoration and management interventions [69]. More specifically, they can be categorised as ecosystem restoration approaches, issue-specific ecosystem-related approaches, infrastructure-related approaches, ecosystem-based management approaches, and ecosystem protection approaches [32]. NBS in marine and coastal governance (or blue NBS) have seldom been studied or implemented [77], which explains the focus of this article on blue NBS.

Indeed, most policies incorporating NBS currently deal with urban areas [54,82] or forests [52], especially at local – and not regional or European - levels [42].

Despite growing recognition of the benefits of (blue) NBS, their uptake across Europe remains uneven [15]. After having established promising research programs on NBS, policymakers are now struggling to move from conceptualisation to policy adoption and implementation of NBS [56,77]. The adoption of NBS is critical for achieving multiple policy objectives outlined in the international and European Union’s (EU) strategic frameworks, including the Sustainable Development Goals, the European Green Deal, and the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030.

This article underlines the main barriers to the adoption of blue NBS at the EU level. This paper also makes two important contributions for policymakers and practitioners: (1) it develops policy recommendations to tackle the identified barriers to blue NBS adoption and (2) it identifies EU-level policy opportunities. They are structured based on the steps of the policy cycle – for each step, challenges and barriers, and policy opportunities and recommendations are developed.

Section 2 develops the theoretical framework of the policy cycle adapted to the EU level. Section 3 provides a definition and examples of blue NBS. Section 4 gives an overview of the material and methods used.

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Section 5 identifies the barriers to blue NBS adoption at the EU level. Section 6 develops policy recommendations. Finally, policy opportunities and the conclusion are developed in Section 7.

2. The EU policy cycle

Conceptualizing the policy process is important to provide a systematic overview of how policymaking occurs and what are the different steps followed by policy actors. To do so, researchers have used the policy cycle concept [50]. Although slightly different versions of it co-exist in the literature, most conceptualizations of the policy cycle include at least five steps¹: (1) agenda-setting; (2) policy formulation; (3) decision-making; (4) policy implementation; (5) policy evaluation [37,88]. This policy cycle can be applied to the EU policy-making process. The starting point, agenda-setting, is usually associated with a policy problem definition, where the European Council sets political guidelines for EU policies [1]. In addition, the Commission can set the agenda through the publication of green and white papers [44]. Eventually, only the Commission has the right to initiative in the EU [75].

The policy formulation stage starts with the impact assessment process, which then leads to the adoption of a policy proposal by the EC [44]. The process of policy formulation at the EU level should follow the Better Regulation (BR) guidelines, with impact assessments as a supporting tool [74,85]. Impact assessments are gathering the informational resources, evidence and stakeholder input, used for policy formulation [37]. They are procedural tools to follow to formulate EU policies as ‘IAs must set out the logical reasoning that links the problem, its underlying causes, the objectives and a range of policy options to tackle the problem. They must present the likely [economic, social, and environmental] impacts of the options, who will be affected by them and how’ ([22], p.14).

Once a policy proposal from the Commission services is out, the decision-making step can begin, with the Council of the EU and the European Parliament (EP) acting as co-legislators in most cases [11]. A new mode of dealing with decision-making has become more and more common in the last years, through discussions and negotiations in trilogues [57]. Trilogues are informal meetings between representatives of the EC, the Council of the EU and the EP, where they try to reach an agreement that will then be easily adopted formally² [58].

Once a policy is adopted, comes the time for policy implementation, ‘the execution or enforcement of a policy by the responsible institutions and organisations’ ([51], p. 51). At the EU level, and especially regarding environmental policies, two separate steps of policy implementation can be identified. The first is final policy formation, during which a lot of decision-making still needs to occur (implementing acts by the EC or by Member States’ authorities) because implementing a policy brings new issues on the agenda – there is therefore an implementation and decision-making overlap [6]. When policy formation is finished, comes policy delivery, which consists of ‘putting in practice the policy instruments’ ([6], p. 17). Empirically, this translates into three types of outputs: (1) formal outputs – legal and administrative measures to transpose EU law, (2) practical outputs – administrative implementation through national regulatory practices; and (3) practical application – behavioural change and compliance of addressees [95].

Finally, the last step of the policy cycle, policy evaluation, encompasses the assessment of policy outputs and outcomes and leads to a decision to terminate, continue or adapt the policy in question [51]. It has become ‘an established feature of EU environmental policymaking ([81], p. 366). Usually, the evaluations of existing policies are then used

as a basis for policy adaptation, in most cases through the impact assessment process [44].

3. Blue Nature-Based Solutions

There are three main definitions of NBS (see [70]). Because this paper looks at EU policies, the definition provided by the European Commission is used and adapted to marine and coastal ecosystems. Blue NBS are ‘solutions that are inspired and supported by nature, which are cost-effective, simultaneously provide environmental, social, and economic benefits and help build resilience. Such solutions bring more, and more diverse, nature and natural features and processes into seascapes, through locally adapted, resource-efficient and systemic interventions. They must benefit biodiversity and support the delivery of a range of ecosystem services’ [70], p.2).

Blue NBS can be divided into three categories [73]. First, protection (fully, highly, lightly, or minimally protected), with for example marine protected areas (MPAs). MPAs are protection tools designed to protect biodiversity and promote more resilient marine ecosystems and to increase their social benefits [41]. Second, there are restoration activities, with five possible categories: passive, active, partial, rehabilitation, and ecosystem creation [73]. Restorative activities are ‘deliberate interventions for recovering ecosystem attributes that have been lost or degraded ([39] in [73], p.7). For example, coastal ecosystems such as wetlands, mangroves, seagrass beds, coral reefs, barrier dunes and beaches are currently restored to ensure natural coastal protection against storms and floods. For coastal vegetated ecosystems and biogenic reefs (such as oyster reefs), blue NBS consist of both decreasing outside sourced vulnerability (i.e. anthropic pressures from land and sea) and improving onsite their functionality so they can better adapt to sea level rise. While for reef, micro-fragmentation techniques allow for fast reef restoration after hurricanes and increase coral cover,³ for mangroves, activities consist of restoring the water flow circulation within and with the adjacent areas. For oyster reefs that grow vertically, activities rely to set up natural walls to attract and latch oyster larvae that drift through the water and forbid the dragging in these areas [40]. Finally, there are other management measures that are not protection or restoration activities. They include for example temporary fisheries closures and/or banning particular types of fishing gear, regulations banning a specific practice (e.g. anchoring in an area of protected marine plant species), or encouraging/supporting the development of less destructive economic activities [73].

When consulting practitioners involved in marine and coastal ecosystems, they point out to three main challenges that (blue) NBS are facing. The first one is the lack of policy driver and appropriate legislation. The second one is the lack of funding mechanisms, and the third priority challenge is the lack of primary stakeholder awareness and engagement ([69]. Because the literature does not seem to point out to a lack of interest from policymakers in (blue) NBS – but rather to a lack of knowledge and awareness – it is relevant to investigate what are the barriers to their adoption in the context of the EU.

4. Material and methods

For this article, three main types of materials have been used. First and foremost, scientific articles from the literature. Although a systematic approach has not been followed,⁴ the articles used were retrieved from Google Scholar using the following inquiries: ‘nature-

¹ Policy formulation and decision-making are sometimes considered as only one step. However, they are two steps of the EU policy process as different actors are involved in them through different processes [44].

² ‘Early agreements’ = legislation adopted thanks to an informal compromise in trilogue.

³ See <https://www.coralvita.co/>

⁴ A systematic approach was not adopted because of its lack of relevance for the specific scope of the article –wider research on NBS was returning thousands of articles, and more refined research on blue NBS in marine and coastal ecosystems and policies was not giving enough relevant literature (around 25 articles).

based solutions', 'EU', 'marine and coastal governance', 'blue nature-based solutions' and 'marine nature-based solutions'. The second type of sources is official documents and reports, mostly from the EC or other European bodies. Some legal documents were also used for this paper, including directives, regulations, strategies, communications, etc. Relevant sources in this regard have been selected because of their contribution to EU policy in three main areas: biodiversity conservation and restoration, climate change adaptation, and marine and coastal policies. This selection comes primarily from Ferraro and Failler [32] and Ferraro et al. [33]. It has been updated to include the newest developments that happened in the last few years, including the EU nature restoration law. Finally, research outputs from MaCoBioS have also been used as material for this paper. This project covers nine case studies in three eco-regions with different climates (tropical, temperate, and oceanic/cold) and undergoing different effects of climate change: Northern Europe (Ireland, Norway, the UK), North-Western Mediterranean (France, Italy, Spain), and the Lesser Antilles in the Caribbean (Barbados, Bonaire, Martinique). The project, as well as this paper, focus on nature-based solutions in marine and coastal ecosystems (here called 'blue' NBS). This is relevant because the implementation of NBS in marine and coastal ecosystems has been slower than on land, because of their interconnected socio-ecological nature [70]. Indeed, marine and coastal NBS have to be designed and implemented at the seascape level, which poses more challenges than in clearly delimited ecosystems, as showed at the EU level by the difficulties around the adoption of integrated coastal zone management plans [87].

Those documents were selected for their relevance regarding the barriers to and policy opportunities for the adoption of NBS. The document analysis was conducted to identify policy barriers to the adoption of NBS in the literature (Section 5), to formulate policy recommendations for the uptake of NBS based on an analysis of EU policy documents (Section 6); and to emphasize policy opportunities for the inclusion of NBS in marine-related EU policies (Section 7).

5. Barriers to the adoption of blue NBS in EU policies

The adoption of (blue) NBS faces many obstacles in different steps of the policy cycle. First, they are not prioritized in policy agendas [34] [agenda-setting]. Second, the identification of challenges, the objectives to be achieved and the actions to complete the policy goals are often incoherent [35] [policy formulation & decision-making]. Third, adopted regulations are not adequate to support NBS implementation because of regulatory gaps or inconsistencies that may hinder their uptake or effectiveness [68] and because of insufficient funding and investments [34] [policy implementation]. Finally, there is a need for frameworks to assess NBS impacts on several challenges and at different geographic scales [34,83] [policy evaluation].

This section develops the barriers to the uptake of NBS by following the steps of the policy cycle identified.

5.1. Agenda-setting: lack of political awareness and will

Over the last few years, NBS have slowly appeared in political agendas [63]. However, moving NBS from the top of the EU research and innovation agenda [43,97] to the political agenda remains challenging for several reasons [14].

First, the low awareness of politicians and civil servants translates into a lack of political support [34], which prevents NBS from appearing on the political agenda. This lack of awareness of the potential of NBS is further reinforced by a low sense of urgency among decision-makers [80].

Second, it is challenging for policymakers because they also need to take economic and social demands into account, while evaluating policy options as fast as possible, within the timeframe of the EC political cycle (five years) [64]. This challenge is reinforced by a lack of political will [12], changing political priorities and the lack of long-term planning as

related obstacles [69].

Finally, there is a structural issue of insufficient public funding, which appears as a barrier to even entering the policy cycle, although it is an issue more directly related to the implementation step of the policy cycle [16,34].

In practice, three main areas of action for NBS are privileged on the EU agenda in the next years⁵: (1) advancing NBS knowledge and data; (2) closing the NBS research-implementation gap; (3) mainstreaming the role of R&I in NBS policy; and (4) exchange, capacity building, and awareness [19].

5.2. Policy formulation: lack of cross-sectoral cooperation and coherence

Once policymakers have decided to put NBS into the political agenda, the policy formulation step begins. Policy fragmentation and incoherence, the first main challenge for NBS to be included in policy formulation, has been witnessed in many policy and political settings. The second main challenge relates to the difficulty of moving from the declaration of intention on NBS (agenda-setting) to formulating policies that include them (policy formulation).

First, the fragmentation of existing policy frameworks on marine conservation, fisheries management, coastal development and climate adaptation makes it hard to integrate NBS into policies [31]. This fragmentation is especially problematic because policies are developed in a sectoral manner. At the same time, the challenges, such as climate change adaptation, biodiversity restoration and sustainable development, that they should tackle are interdependent and cannot be addressed separately [67,93]. Moreover, NBS cannot be implemented and deliver all of their benefits without a cross-sectoral approach as they have effects on multiple ecosystems [36]. Policy coherence is therefore one of the first steps to be taken to facilitate the uptake and implementation of NBS [10].

The second issue is that, although strategic documents and communications acknowledge the importance of promoting and implementing NBS, this does not translate into the adopted policy frameworks. Biodiversity conservation is mainly approached through the EU-wide strategic document that was adopted in 1998 and updated regularly since then – the EU Biodiversity Strategy. This strategic document was adopted in the framework of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and in compliance with the Aichi targets [38]. The major directives in EU environmental policies are the Birds Directive and Habitats Directive ("Nature directives"), the Water Framework Directive, and the Marine Strategy Framework Directive, which is the first legislative instrument that aims to protect marine biodiversity [46]. They reflect the sectoral and fragmented approach to biodiversity conservation in Europe. However, the adoption of the European Green Deal (COM(2019) 640 final) in 2019 and of the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 (COM(2020) 380 final) in 2020, shows the EC's commitment to developing its biodiversity conservation and restoration policies. The interdependence between biodiversity restoration and climate change adaptation, as well as the need to promote NBS, are acknowledged in the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030. Some policy recommendations to transform the intentions set in the Biodiversity Strategy into concrete policies will be developed in Section 5.

5.3. Decision-making: ill-adapted governance arrangements

The adoption of NBS in marine and coastal ecosystems (MCE) requires policy interventions that cover several landscapes and seascapes, cross different jurisdictional boundaries and involve many actors from different levels of governance (from local to international level) [83].

⁵ See European Roadmap to 2030 for Research and Innovation on Nature-based Solutions, https://www.biodiversa.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/EU-RI-Roadmap_web.pdf [accessed on 30/04/2024]

For these reasons, existing governance arrangements are sometimes problematic and prevent NBS from being adopted [36,71]. Research has shown that collaborative partnerships reassembling practitioners and stakeholders are not focused on NBS [4]. This governance gap hinders the design of NBS, as demonstrated by experience in urban planning policies, where the knowledge of NBS is more advanced [36,96]. Therefore, a rapid change in governance arrangements is urgently needed [92].

At the EU level, several actors are also involved in the decision-making process. Once the policy proposal is adopted by the Commission, it needs to be approved by the co-legislators, i.e. the European Parliament and the Council [5].⁶ More specifically in MCE governance, the responsible DG is the one in charge of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries⁷ (DG MARE). DG MARE collaborates for some aspects with two other DGs responsible for environment (DG ENV) and climate (DG CLIMA). Other important actors are the EU Member States (MS); they vote on EU legislation through the Council and are responsible for the implementation of EU policies. In MS, a multitude of national, regional and local actors intervene during policy implementation, in addition to private actors with diverging interests. Finally, the international level should not be overlooked as the EU and its MS also have international obligations regarding MCE governance (PROJECT D4.1).

Efforts to coordinate those different actors involved in decision-making, and to facilitate stakeholder dialogue and knowledge sharing are necessary – policy recommendations in that regard will be developed in Section 5.

5.4. Policy implementation: lack of appropriate funding and weak policy frameworks

At the step of policy implementation, appropriate funding and strong policy frameworks are necessary to ensure the policy is effectively implemented and delivers its benefits.

Regarding funding, NBS have been a priority area for investment under the funding programme of the EC “Horizon 2020” in terms of research funding and over 200 million euros of spending by the EC have been identified as NBS-related by 2020 [10,76]. However, this funding concerns research and innovation and not policies that are implementing NBS in actual ecosystems, such as MCE. Moreover, only less than 5 % of climate-related finance is dedicated to climate impact mitigation, with less than 1 % dedicated to coastal protection, which includes NBS [83]. In that sense, adequate funding of policies is critical to go further than research and to support the planning, implementation, and monitoring of blue NBS [4,80]. This need for financial flows as an enabling condition for NBS has been pointed out by the IUCN, which reports that a majority of Nationally Determined Conditions render NBS adoption and implementation conditional to external financing [84]. Research also supports the idea that sustainable NBS can only be achieved through long-term financing and investments and can contribute to the establishment of a green economy [61,68].

Existing policy frameworks linked to the governance of MCE through NBS are covering two policy sectors: climate change mitigation and biodiversity conservation/restoration. Climate change was first addressed in an EU adaptation strategy in 2013. More recently, under the impulsion of the European Green Deal, a new adaptation strategy [23] and a European Climate Law [24] have been adopted. Although the

⁶ As explained in section 2, the use of trilogues should not be overlooked when it comes to environmental decision-making.

⁷ The three main missions of DG MARE are: (1) to ensure that the ocean resources are used sustainably and that coastal communities and the fishing sector have a prosperous future; (2) to promote maritime policies and stimulate a sustainable blue economy; and (3) to promote ocean governance at international level (see https://commission.europa.eu/about-european-commission/departments-and-executive-agencies/maritime-affairs-and-fisheries_en)

Commission committed to proposing NBS in its adaptation strategy, only two references to NBS are found in the European Climate Law. This regulation asks Member States to promote NBS to adapt to climate change and acknowledges that ‘Nature-based solutions, in particular, can benefit climate change mitigation, adaptation, and biodiversity protection’ (European Climate Law, recital 32).

Efforts have been made over the past years, through the proposal of a regulation on nature restoration, in which a holistic approach to nature restoration is proposed [45]. In this policy proposal, different (annex-based) regimes are developed by ecosystems: terrestrial, coastal and freshwater ecosystems (article 4), marine ecosystems (article 5), urban ecosystems (article 6), rivers and floodplains (article 7), pollinator populations (article 8), agricultural ecosystems (article 9) and forest ecosystems (article 10) [45]. This constitutes the first attempt to fill the gaps in existing directives and contribute to the fulfilment of the international obligations contracted through the United Nations Convention on Climate Change, the Paris Agreement, and the UN Convention on Biological Diversity [47]. In addition, this policy proposal requires Member States to promote NBS to restore the good condition of ecosystems and mitigate climate change, also with several mentions of the European Climate Law [26]. It was adopted on 17th June 2024 (entry into force on 18th August 2024) after intense political debate. While this constitutes a step towards integrating biodiversity and climate change policies and strengthening the policy frameworks, it still relies very much on targets from existing legislation. Its strict implementation by Member States should be followed very closely.

The implementation of NBS requires more robust policy frameworks that develop proper requirements for NBS and targets to be attained, with adequate funding to support it. Related policy recommendations are developed in Section 5.

5.5. Policy evaluation: need for monitoring and indicators

The policy evaluation step is not usually presented as a barrier or a challenge to blue NBS. It is however most commonly addressed through the formulation of recommendations for the uptake and implementation of blue NBS [69,94]. Therefore, recommendations based on the literature are developed in Section 5.5.

6. Policy recommendations for the uptake of blue NBS

The next sub-sections outline policy recommendations intended to overcome the barriers identified in Section 4. Furthermore, some more practical guidelines are established, to highlight existing EU-level policy opportunities to implement those recommendations and guidelines. Both are following the policy cycle steps developed in Section 2.

6.1. Agenda-setting: increase political commitment to (blue) NBS

Although political awareness and commitment towards (blue) NBS is generally problematic, it does not appear to be such an issue at the European level. Indeed, the European Roadmap to 2030 for Research and Innovation on Nature-based Solutions already established priority actions to be taken on NBS in the next years (see section 4.1.). But, to move from research on NBS towards the actual adoption and implementation of NBS, some more political commitment would be necessary. For example, better information and practical examples of blue NBS [69] or the involvement of citizens and stakeholders in policy-making fora [64] could support political commitment to blue NBS.

6.2. Policy formulation: integrate NBS into policy framework through cross-sectoral cooperation and policy coherence

The analysis of EU policy documents⁸ shows that, although the EC acknowledges the interdependence between climate change adaptation and biodiversity conservation/restoration, it has not been yet possible to transfer this into a comprehensive and holistic policy framework [12]. Despite the innovative approach of the EU nature restoration law, this legislative instrument still develops separate regimes by ecosystems and does not go further than asking for the promotion of NBS. Additionally, it faced strong political resistance before being finally adopted.

Policy approaches also remain fragmented between interconnected ecosystems, which prevents NBS from being adopted and implemented in EU policies (cf. Nature Restoration Law). Indeed, the adoption and implementation of NBS in MCEs have also been challenged by the division between land and sea management, which does not acknowledge the impact that landscapes have on seascapes [70].

Because of the separate approaches by ecosystems in existing EU policies (Biodiversity Strategy; existing directives; and Nature Restoration Law), NBS are harder to implement and their positive effects on ecological status in MCEs cannot be delivered [48]. In this regard, the uptake and implementation of NBS are more developed in urban areas [90]. In some experimental applications (at the city level) of NBS, researchers found that they only work when approached through a cross- and multi-sectoral coordination including business and industries, environmental policy actors, representatives from natural resource management, ecological conservation and restoration, disaster and risk reduction etc. [12].

The main recommendations with the goal of policy coordination and coherence are (1) to acknowledge the interdependence between the different ecosystems and the consequences of land-based activities in marine and coastal ecosystems; (2) to develop integrated, cross-sectoral policies and strategies that incorporate blue NBS into broader frameworks for marine conservation, coastal management, fisheries, climate adaptation, and sustainable development, and (3) to integrate existing frameworks into one that considers all societal challenges and several policy sectors, based on existing international and EU policies. The main recommendations regarding the integration of NBS into existing policies are (1) to explicitly require the integration of NBS in national policy instruments developed by Member States (e.g. Nature Restoration Plans); (2) to introduce mandatory requirements, targets and policy objectives in terms of NBS adoption and implementation in EU directives and regulations in the environmental and climate change sectors related to, but not limited to, marine and coastal ecosystem; (3) to establish clear policy objectives; and (4) to establish clear guidelines and standards to facilitate the integration of blue NBS into EU policies.

More practically, the integration of NBS in (marine) policies through impact assessment would allow for a multi-dimensional analysis of their costs and benefits, which is regularly asked by many public and private stakeholders [4,83]. Adopting (marine) NBS in policies going through impact assessment would also contribute to tackling the challenge of coherence between the identification of challenges, objectives to be achieved and actions to complete policy goals. Furthermore, NBS should be automatically considered in strategy planning, land use planning and infrastructure development, to make sure that they are used in coastal and marine management. To do so, the use of ecosystem-based approaches and spatial planning tools (e.g. Integrated Coastal Zone Management) would be helpful to identify priority areas for the implementation of NBS and to increase synergies with existing

⁸ For an extensive review of international and EU policies on biodiversity and climate change, consult Authors (2021), Review report on Nature-Based Solutions stakeholders and policy, PROJECT Deliverable 4.1, accessible here; an extensive overview of NBS in EU and international contexts can also be found in [18].

initiatives. Although ICZM is recommended in the Marine Spatial Planning Directive (MSPD), no planning tool is compulsory for EU Member States to use in their marine spatial plans [59]. An improvement of the EU legislation could be to make ICZM in marine spatial planning compulsory and to integrate some elements regarding the use of marine NBS in this approach. Such a change could occur through the revision of the MSPD and would contribute to the mainstreaming of NBS in EU marine policies.

6.3. Decision-making: develop more adapted and policy-oriented governance arrangements

The creation of a multi-stakeholder platform on blue NBS would facilitate engagement and collaboration while also bringing more knowledge to integrate NBS into marine policies. This platform would need to involve all types of actors from the different levels of MCEs' governance [10] to also facilitate policy coordination, coherence and implementation. The relevant actors have been identified (adapted from [33]). At the international level, they are: the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN), the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), the Oceanographic Commission Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), the Global Environmental Facility Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES), and the World Bank (WB). At the European level, the relevant actors are: the European Commission (specifically DG MARE, ENV, and CLIMA, and the Joint Research Centre), the European Environmental Agency (EEA), the European Investment Bank (EIB), EU Member States/regional and local authorities, the European Parliament (EP), and the 2015 EU Expert Group on Nature-Based Solutions. Finally, a number of NGOs and networks have been identified as relevant, they include: the Nature-Based Solutions Initiative, the World Wildlife Fund for Nature (WWF), Fauna & Flora International, Conservation International, Oceana, Sea Shepherd, the Global Coral Reef Alliance, the International Coral Reef Initiative, Reef Check, and Wetlands International.

The recommendation is to give a political mandate [3] to a single actor (e.g. DG MARE/ENV or EEA) to work on blue NBS for EU policies. If the mandate given is only for blue NBS, DG MARE would be more indicated. But if the mandate is for NBS to encompass all relevant policy fields – terrestrial, coastal and freshwater ecosystems, marine ecosystems, urban ecosystems, river and floodplains, agricultural ecosystems, and forest ecosystems – then the best actor to do so would be DG ENV or the European Environmental Agency. Based on this mandate, a multi-stakeholder platform could be launched, with some participants to the EU Expert Group on NBS as well as representatives from the international levels, NGOs and networks, but also national, regional and local actors. There needs to be a mix of public and private actors from all levels to make sure that all interests are considered and that concrete blue NBS can be pushed towards adoption and implementation, with as much support as possible.

Through this multistakeholder platform focused on blue NBS, the idea is also to promote knowledge exchange and to develop capacity-building activities for NBS adoption and implementation. On this task, the European Environmental Agency could take the lead to serve as a knowledge broker for NBS [53] and to allow lesson drawing on NBS implementation between policy fields (e.g. lessons from NBS in urban areas for NBS adoption and implementation in MCEs). Additionally, the literature on NBS emphasizes the importance of stakeholder participation during policy formulation and evaluation to contribute to NBS effectiveness [63,89].

The policy and regulatory frameworks should also support the adoption of NBS, streamline permitting procedures and remove administrative barriers to facilitate the implementation of NBS projects. Some frameworks to choose between policy options have also been

recently development. First, there is an assessment framework that supports policymakers in choosing between NBS and traditional options [8]. Second, another conceptual framework has been developed to choose appropriate NBS depending on the types of challenges that policymakers want to tackle [73]. The intervention options developed in this framework are the protection of marine and coastal ecosystems (e.g. marine protected areas), restoration activities (passive or active ecosystem restoration, partial restoration, rehabilitation, or ecosystem creation), or other management measures (e.g. regulatory interventions to ban or regulate a specific practice in a particular ecosystem).

6.4. Policy implementation: provide adequate funding and strengthen policy frameworks

Dedicated funding streams need to be allocated to blue NBS projects through existing EU programs, such as the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF), LIFE program, Horizon Europe, and the Blue Economy⁹ Strategy implementation. This funding should support governments, businesses and civil society organisations in the implementation of NBS. Different instruments already exist in this regard, including the Communication on a new approach for a sustainable blue economy [25] and the subsequently developed sustainability criteria for the blue economy,¹⁰ which still need to be integrated by EU and national policymakers. In addition, the Bioeconomy strategy and its action plan (2018),¹¹ which were promising tools to fund NBS, should be evaluated and improved for the next years. Moreover, the BlueInvest initiative (2019),¹² funded by the EMFAF, which was supposed to support public-private partnerships in the blue economy, also needs to be appraised and updated if necessary. Finally, monitoring and strengthening the application of the EU Taxonomy for sustainable activities¹³ is important to identify nature-negative divestment and redirect financing to NBS [61,72]. Importantly, those different funding strategies should be adapted to the specificities of NBS and their economic value [60].

The existing (and future) funding mechanisms should support increased investment in NBS, notably by demonstrating the economic, social and environmental returns on investments that NBS can provide [60]. Natural capital accounting¹⁴ could support this. In this regard, the adoption of the Commission's proposal for a regulation introducing new environmental economic accounts models [27] is crucial. Other innovative financing mechanisms could be used to mobilise private investment [7] in NBS such as green bonds [72], conservation funds, impact investing, corporate social responsibility initiatives, and public-private partnerships [61] to mobilize additional resources for Blue NBS. Possible innovative funding mechanisms could be [49]: (1) the creation of biodiversity, wetlands and blue credits by extending the carbon credit market to cover biodiversity and other ecosystems; (2) the creation of an ecosystem service tax that would be implemented to local or national levels to generate income for NBS implementation; (3) improve resource management by the use of key indicators for contracting NBS services.

Finally, some smaller changes could also contribute to NBS uptake and implementation, such as the investment in data collection to

⁹ More information can be found in European Investment Bank [30] Clean oceans and the blue economy: overview 2023, <https://www.eib.org/attachm ents/lucalli/20220311-clean-oceans-and-the-blue-economy-overview-2023.pdf> (accessed on 24th January 2025).

¹⁰ European Commission: European Climate,[29].

¹¹ European Commission[28].

¹² European Commission. BlueInvest[21].

¹³ European Commission[20].

¹⁴ Natural capital accounting is a tool to measure the changes in the stock and condition of natural capital (ecosystems) at a variety of scales and to integrate the flow and value of ecosystem services into accounting and reporting systems in a standard way (European Commission. Natural capital accounting. https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/nature-and-biodiversity/natural-capital-accounting_en).

enhance the understanding of ecosystem services thanks to the monitoring of their ecological status. Another way to advance NBS in policies is to prioritise them through funding - by providing preferential funding for NBS actions that address both climate change adaptation and mitigation and support sustainable development and biodiversity. To make sure that NBS will be implemented and effective, it is crucial to ensure equitable distribution of funding to support Blue NBS projects in coastal communities, small island states, and other vulnerable areas disproportionately affected by marine degradation and climate change.

6.5. Policy evaluation: mainstreaming blue NBS into policy-making processes

Lessons from urban policies implementing NBS tell us that evaluation of those solutions is necessary, which includes the need for monitoring through shared and clear indicators and ex-post assessments [65]. Importantly, those indicators should be used to evaluate the effectiveness of NBS [86]. Therefore, it is recommended to develop monitoring and evaluation mechanisms for NBS to (1) make sure that they are properly implemented and (2) to evaluate their short- and long-term impacts and effectiveness [77,78]. Several assessment frameworks have been developed in the last years to assess (blue) NBS impacts, effectiveness and efficiency [8,17,55,63,76,91]. Therefore, some robust monitoring and evaluation mechanisms should be developed to evaluate the implementation of NBS and to measure their impact on ecological status, biodiversity conservation/restoration, climate change, and socio-economic resilience [66,9]. To do so, adaptive management approaches could be developed [70], with compulsory evaluation and feedback to refine NBS based on scientific evidence, stakeholder consultation and lessons learnt from monitoring and evaluation.

Based on evaluation outputs, NBS should be streamlined throughout the policy cycle by being automatically considered during policy design and formulation linked to MCEs. At the European level, this should happen during the impact assessment analyses, when different policy interventions are developed and compared [74]. Indeed, impact assessment has already been found to be a key step for the mainstreaming of NBS in urban areas [89] and to support policy-making as well as effective NBS implementation [2]. An additional measure to reinforce this would be to extend the scope of the Environmental Impact Assessment directive [61], which outlines major building and development projects for which an EIA is required.

Some tools exist, such as MAES, which can be used to map and assess ecosystems, their services, and their economic values. It was developed at the European level to incorporate those values into EU and national accounting and reporting systems [62].

7. Conclusion and policy opportunities¹⁵

This paper presented the barriers to the adoption of blue NBS in each step of the EU policy cycle. They include the lack of political awareness and will (agenda-setting), the lack of cross-sectoral cooperation and policy coherence (policy formulation), ill-adapted governance arrangements (decision-making), the lack of appropriate funding and weak policy frameworks (policy implementation), and the need for monitoring and indicators (policy evaluation). Then, policy recommendations were developed to support the uptake of marine NBS in EU policies at every step of the process. The main recommendations were to increase political commitment to blue NBS through better information and stakeholder engagement (agenda-setting), to integrate blue NBS in cross-sectoral policies (policy formulation), to develop more policy-oriented governance arrangements under the responsibility of one EU actor (decision-making), to provide adequate funding and strengthen

¹⁵ A recapitulative table of NBS features, practitioners' challenges, barriers to NBS and policy solutions is provided in Annex 1.

policy frameworks (policy implementation), and to mainstream blue NBS in the EU policy-making process (policy evaluation).

To conclude on the policy recommendations, policy instruments and opportunities exist. Several types of policy instruments are available to integrate (blue) NBS into marine policies [13,54]. First, supporting the creation and diffusion of knowledge and innovative instruments such as communication campaigns to raise awareness or inform about NBS options, campaigns targeted at citizens or community groups to inform and explain new NBS regulations, targeted educational programs, certifications through labels or ranks, workshops, pilot projects, etc. Second, adopting economic and fiscal instruments, which include market-based incentive schemes, subsidies, public-private partnerships, taxes, trading of permits, and public grants, for the adoption and implementation of NBS. On economic and fiscal instruments, the EU Investment Bank [49] recommends a radical change in market structure through regulatory interventions building direct incentives for private entities. Regulatory intervention to remedy the lack of financial support for NBS could take three forms: (1) Rewards: financial payments for ecosystem services through NBS projects; (2) Punishment: creation of codes (e.g. urban building code requirement for new buildings to have green roofs) adapted to marine and coastal ecosystems where private entities that did not consider NBS in their investments are punished; and (3) Cap and trade markets: create regulatory limits on biodiversity loss and create a trading market for them (e.g. carbon emission trading schemes). Third, designing and ensuring the implementation of legislative, regulatory, and strategic instruments, which take the form of legislative texts, strategies, plans or standards to force policy actors to engage and comply with policies that support NBS adoption and implementation. It is important here to include quantitative targets to be reached as to the ecosystem services that should be protected, restored or created. Fourth, developing agreement-based/cooperative instrument, through mechanisms that support citizens' and stakeholders' engagement and

cooperation (e.g. citizens assemblies, community management of certain spaces) or exchange platforms to support regional planning and action.

Finally, EU policy opportunities are also available to put the recommendations from Section 5 into practice. There are opportunities to increase coordination, coherence and integration of blue NBS in (1) extending coordination between policies developed under the umbrella of the European Green Deal; (2) the implementation of the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 and the next EU Biodiversity Strategy; (3) the revision of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive; (4) a more ambitious Nature Restoration Law; (5) drawing lessons from urban planning policies where NBS have been implemented and evaluated. Policy opportunities also exist for the funding of blue NBS through the European Maritime Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (BlueInvest); the Blue Economy Strategy; the introduction of sustainability criteria through the Sustainable blue economy communication; the Bioeconomy strategy; the use of the EU taxonomy for sustainable activities; and the proposal for a regulation introducing new environmental economic account models [27].

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Failler Pierre: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Frehen Lise:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Ferraro Gianluca:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Annex 1. . Recapitulative table of policy solutions

NBS features ^a	Practitioner' challenges ^b	Barriers identified in the paper	Policy solutions proposed in the paper
Inspired and supported by nature	Clarity of definition and concept Data gaps, lack of evidence & coherent access to data	/	/
At seascape level Requires systemic intervention	Challenge of collaboration and interdisciplinary working Lack of organizational capacity	Lack of cross-sectoral cooperation and coherence Ill-adapted governance arrangements	Cross-sectoral cooperation and policy coherence (Section 6.2) Policy-oriented governance arrangements (Section 6.3)
Needs to be adapted locally	Locating suitable interventions	Lack of cross-sectoral cooperation and coherence Ill-adapted governance arrangements	Cross-sectoral cooperation and policy coherence (Section 6.2) Policy-oriented governance arrangements (Section 6.3)
Cost-effective and provide environmental, social, and economic benefits Help building resilience Support the delivery of a range of ecosystem services Benefit biodiversity	Lack of stakeholder awareness and engagement/Time constraints	Lack of political awareness and will Lack of cross-sectoral cooperation and coherence	Increase political commitment (Section 6.1) Cross-sectoral cooperation and policy coherence (Section 6.2)
Resource efficient	Lack of funding mechanisms Uncertainty in management and outcomes Monitory and evaluating effectiveness	Lack of appropriate funding Need for monitoring and indicators	Provide adequate funding (Section 6.4) Mainstreaming into policy-making processes (Section 6.5)

^aDefinition of the European Commission. See O'Leary et al. [69]. Practitioner insights on challenges and options for advancing blue Nature-based Solutions. Marine Policy, 163, 106104.

^bBased on O'Leary et al. [69] Practitioner insights on challenges and options for advancing blue Nature-based Solutions. Marine Policy, 163, 106104.

Data Availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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